

Review of Capital Structure with reference to selected BSE Listed Companies

Yuvraj D. Nalwade¹, Mahavir M. Shetiya² and Atul Kumar³

¹Assistant Professor, Vidya Pratishthan's Institute of Information Technology, Pune, MH, India.

²Assistant Professor, SNG Institute of Management & Research, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

³Assistant Professor, Siddhant College of Engineering, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

CITATION: Nalwade, Yuvraj D.; Shetiya, Mahavir M. and Kumar, Atul (2016), "Review of Capital Structure with reference to selected BSE Listed Companies", *MERC Global's International Journal of Social Science & Management*, Vol. 3, Issue 5, pp. 150-154.

ARTICLE HISTORY: Submitted: September 29, 2016, Revision received: October 20, 2016, Accepted: October 28, 2016

ARTICLE TYPE: Research paper

ABSTRACT

Indian corporates employ a substantial amount of debt in their capital structure in terms of the debt-equity ratio as well as total debt to total assets ratio. Nonetheless, foreign-controlled companies in India use less debt than domestic companies. The dependence of the Indian corporate sector on debt as a source of finance has over the year inclined particularly since the mid-nineties. This paper covered the study of different factors that are affecting capital structure decisions. The review of the literature found that almost ten factors are affecting capital structure decisions, but it is difficult to find out the influence efficiency of them. Therefore, in this paper, researchers tried to find the same through the different statistical tests.

KEYWORDS: Debt-equity ratio, Factors, Bombay Stock Exchange Capital Structure.

1. INTRODUCTION

This research is descriptive and analytical research because in descriptive research it contains components of both qualitative and quantitative research. Descriptive research defines the situation as it is. There is no control of the researcher on the selected variables. In this research, data is not manipulated as such. The researcher has defined, explained, analysed and validated different variables. Henceforth, this research is the combination of a descriptive and analytical type of research.

For this study, primary data is not required and used. Secondary data is obtained from various reports, research articles, books, previous research works conducted, Journals, websites, Prowess database package of Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE), 'Handbook of statistics on Indian economy', 'Science direct through the Jaykar Library of Savitribai Phule Pune University' and other published reports, etc. Researchers identified total 139 automobile units were located in Pune and registered under the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE). Based on convenience sampling researchers were selected total 93 companies. The researchers used statistical data analysis. Used the descriptive statistics, selected the input range and then tabs like labels/summary statistics/confidence level.

After this study, the researcher found different facts such as the variables considered for this research are values quoted by the companies in the financial statements. They are picked up so as to measure the impact of them jointly and severally on the capital structure and vice versa. However, all of them are found to be statistically significantly different from each other. As they are assumed to have some relationship with each other theoretically, it is surprising to note that it is not the case.

2. RESEARCH GAP

After the critical analysis of selected literature, it has found that many of the researcher and the authors have focused their research studies in order to evaluate the factors affecting decisions regarding capital structure like working capital, reserves and funds, net worth, asset capital, tangible asset and sales figures of the company. Very few authors and researchers have diversified their studies

towards the analysis of financial statements and their impact on capital structure decisions for companies. Some of the researchers also have considered non-economical and non-financial parameters like managerial strategies, micro and macro-economic factors showing impact on the capital structure decision. It has been observed out of analysed literature that; even though there is a huge significant dependency and relation between stock market performance of the company and capital structure decisions, very negligible research has been conducted to systematically analyse the dependency of capital structure decision on the stock market performance of the company. Except one or two attempts made in order to establish the relation between Earning per share and capital structure decision, no other research body has targeted this area of financial research. So, based on the critical analysis of available literature about selected topic it has been found that it will be very significant to further elaborate the present research body conducted on this topic and hence this has been considered as required field where significant research can be conducted.

2.1. Statement of the research problem

Indian corporates employ a substantial amount of debt in their "Capital structure" in terms of the 'debt-equity ratio' as well as total debt to total assets ratio. Nonetheless, foreign-controlled companies in India use less debt than domestic companies. The dependence of the Indian corporate sector on debt as a source of finance has over the year inclined particularly since the mid-nineties. The corporate enterprises in India seem to prefer long-term borrowings over short-term borrowing. Over the years they seem to have substituted short-term debt for long-term debt.

As a result of debt-dominated "Capital structure", the Indian corporate are exposed to a very high degree of total risk as reflected in high degree of operating leverage and financial leverage and consequently are subject to a high cost of financial distress which includes a broad spectrum of problem ranging from relatively minor liquidity shortages to extreme cases of bankruptcy.

Companies raise funds through various sources, i.e. debt and equity while taking these crucial decision companies have to take into consideration various factors that get affected by "Capital structure" decision and one of the vital factors is the value of shares, hence this problem is taken for study.

3. OBJECTIVES, HYPOTHESIS AND SIGNIFICANCE OF RESEARCH

3.1. Objectives

- To study factors influencing "Capital structure".
- To study the relationship between important factors influencing "Capital structure" with the value of share.

3.2. Hypothesis

The different variables related to "Capital structure" are not having an equal impact on the "Capital structure" of the automobile companies.

3.3. Significance

"Capital structure" which mentions the mix of long term sources of finance such as "equity capital, debentures, term loans and assets" is called to be optimum when collective "cost of capital" is at minimum level. However, in practice, the determination of optimum "Capital structure" is a very difficult task. In designing the "Capital structure" of company, numerous factors are to be taken into account. Lastly, it is assumed that the decision-maker which plays a crucial role in planning of the "Capital structure".

Proper planning is required for designing the "Capital Structure". To determine the "Optimum Capital Structure" that is again huge challenge to firm. If company does not have proper or planned "Capital Structure" then it's dangerous to companies' future growth such a situation will arise financial crunch in future. Unplanned capital Structure Company may be successful in business but that is not sustainable to long run and also such firm is unable to use its financial resources properly. The objective of the current research is to study the various factors that should be considered in mind while formulating the "Capital structure". This study will helpfull for Indian companies as well as stakeholders such as suppliers, Lender, large scale companies, etc. to come out from problem of "Capital structure" decisions.

4. METHODS

The quantitative methodology was employed in this research in order to obtain data so as to address the research objectives. A qualitative study generally attempts to test the theory, in an attempt

to increase the predictive understanding of phenomena and quantitative studies generally attempt to understand phenomena through the meanings that people assign to them. In this, study quantitative approach has been used to satisfy the stated objectives. The research model developed for this study was tested using quantitative method by analyzing data through different statistical tools. The purpose of the study is mainly descriptive and analytical. It is descriptive because descriptive data was collected through financial statements. It is also analytical since it tried to analyse the different factors affecting value of share. In this research the process followed is as under:

- Defining problem statement for research.
- Review of Literature and other studies and theories.
- Methods adopted for data and sample selection & research methodology.
- Interpretation of analysed information and data.
- Presentation of Conclusions Statement.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Descriptive stats of pooled data							
	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation	Kurtosis	Skewness	Count	Confidence Level (95.0%)
Sales	320.51	144.91	542.09	15.47	3.59	93	111.64
Profit after tax	11.76	2.6	36.32	36.38	5.11	93	7.48
Total capital	20.02	8.5	37.07	14.27	3.59	93	7.63
Reserves and funds	87.51	18.23	208.7	31.2	4.99	93	42.98
Net worth	105.72	31.9	216.58	28.45	4.72	93	44.6
Tangible net worth	101.81	27.9	212.85	30.7	4.93	93	43.84
Total term liabilities	64.08	18.55	154.61	41.41	5.81	93	31.84
Net working capital	15.22	1.16	83.6	38.44	5.46	93	17.22
Market Capitalisation	334.65	0	1416.77	28.28	5.26	93	291.78
Beta	0.18	0	0.36	0.78	1.62	93	0.07

In all, 93 companies' data has been pooled together for 10 variables considered for data analysis. Each variable has been explained below:

- **Sales:** The mean sales value is Rs.320.51 crores, with a median at Rs.144.91 crores. The data is positively skewed and platykurtic.
- **Profit after Tax:** The Mean Profit after Tax value is Rs.11.76 crores, with a median at Rs.2.60 crores. The data is positively skewed and platykurtic.
- **Total Capital:** The Mean Total Capital value is Rs.20.02 crores, with a median at Rs.8.50 crores. The data is positively skewed and platykurtic.
- **Reserves:** The Mean Reserves value is Rs.87.51 crores, with a median at Rs.18.23 crores. The data is positively skewed and platykurtic.
- **Net Worth:** The Mean Net Worth value is Rs.105.72 crores, with a median at Rs.31.90 crores. The data is positively skewed and platykurtic.
- **Tangible Net Worth:** The Mean Tangible Net Worth value is Rs.101.81 crores, with a median at Rs.27.90 crores. The data is positively skewed and platykurtic.
- **Total Term Liabilities:** The Mean Total Term Liabilities value is Rs.64.08 crores, with a median at Rs.18.55 crores. The data is positively skewed and platykurtic.
- **Net Working Capital:** The Mean Net Working Capital value is Rs.15.52 crores, with a median at Rs.1.16 crores. The data is positively skewed and platykurtic.
- **Market Capitalisation:** The Mean Market Capitalization value is Rs.334.65 crores, with a median at Rs.0.00 crores. The data is positively skewed and platykurtic.
- **Beta:** The Mean Beta value is Rs.0.18, with a median at Rs.0.00. The data is positively skewed and platykurtic.

5.1. Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis: The different variables related to “Capital structure” are not having an equal impact on the “Capital structure” of the automobile companies.

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distributions of SALES, PAT, TCAP, RESERVES, NW, TNW, TTL, NWC, MCAP and BETA are the same.	Related-Samples Friedman's Two-Way Analysis of Variance by Ranks	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

As the Null Hypothesis is rejected, the alternative hypothesis is proved.

6. CONCLUSION

As the Null Hypothesis is rejected, the alternative hypothesis is proved which means various considered variables such as sales, profit after tax, total capital reserves, etc. are impacting “Capital structure” but it was not having equal impact on “Capital structure” of the automobiles companies.

7. REFERENCES

1. Ali, Azouzi Mohamed and Anis, Jarbouei (2012), “CEO Emotional Bias and Capital Structure Choice Bayesian Network Method”, *Journal of Arts, Science & Commerce*, pp. 14-31.
2. Arsiraphongphisit, Oraluck and Ariff, Mohamed (2004), “Optimal Capital Structure and Firm Value Australian Evidence: 1991 – 2003”, Monash University.
3. Auerbach, Allan J. (1985), “Real Determinants of Corporate Leverage”, in e. Benjamin M. Friedman, *Corporate Capital Structures in the United States*, pp. 301-324, University of Chicago Press.
4. Brennan, M. J. and Shwartz, E. S. (1976), “Corporate Income Taxes, Valuation and The Problem of Optimal Capital Structure”, *Journal of Business*, Vol. 51, pp. 103-114.
5. Caloniris, Charles W. and Hubbard, Glenn (1988), *Firm Heterogeneity, Internal Finance, and Credit Rationing*, National Bureau of Economic Research, Cambridge.
6. Dann, Larry Y. and Mikkleson, Wayne H (1984), “Convertible Debt Issuance, Capital Structure Change And Financing-Related Information”, *Journal of Financial Economics*, Vol. 13, pp. 157-186.
7. Devereux, Michael and Schiantarelli, Fabio (1990), *Investment, Financial Factors, and Cash Flow: Evidence from U.K. Panel Data*, in R. Glenn Hubbard, *Asymmetric Information, Corporate Finance, and Investment*, pp. 279-306, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
8. Fama, Eugene F. (1969), “Efficient Capital Markets: A Review of Theory and Empirical Work”, *The Journal of Finance*, Vol. 25, No. 2, pp. 383-417.
9. Fama, Eugene F. (1991), “Efficient Capital Markets: II”, *The Journal of Finance*, Vol. 46, No. 5, pp. 1575-1617.
10. Frank, Murray Z. and Goyal, Vidhan K. (2009), “Capital Structure Decisions: Which Factors are Reliably Important?”, *Financial Management*, pp. 1-37.
11. Green, Richard C. (1984), “Investment Incentives, Debt, And Warrants”, *Journal of Financial Economics*, Vol. 13, pp. 115-136.
12. Handoo, Anshu and Sharma, Kapil (2014), “A Study on Determinants of Capital Structure in India”, *IIMB Management Review*, pp. 171-182.
13. Hernadi, Peter and Ormos, Mihaly (2012), “What managers think of capital structure and how they act: Evidence from Central and Eastern Europe”, *Baltic Journal of Economics*, pp. 47-71.
14. Hovakimian, Armen (2001), “The Debt-Equity Choice”, *The Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, Vol. 36, No. 1, pp. 1-24.
15. Huang, Samuel G. H. and Song, Frank M. (2002), “The Determinants of Capital Structure: Evidence from China”, Hong Kong: Centre for China Financial Research, The University of Hong Kong.
16. Jensen, Michael C. (1978), “Some Anomalous Evidence Regarding Market Efficiency”, *Journal of Financial Economics*, Vol. 6, No. 2/3, pp. 95-101.
17. Jensen, Michael C. and Meckling, William H. (1976), “Theory of the Firm: Managerial Behavior, Agency Costs and Ownership Structure”, *Journal of Financial Economics*, pp. 305-360.

18. Koralun-Bereznicka, Julia (2013), "How Does Asset Structure Correlate with Capital Structure? – Cross-Industry and Cross-Size Analysis of the EU Countries", *Universal Journal of Accounting and Finance*, Vol. 1, Issue 1, pp. 19-28.
19. Pandey, I. M. (2004), "Capital Structure, Profitability and Market Structure: Evidence from Malaysia", *Asia Pacific Journal of Economics & Business*, Vol. 8, No. 2, pp. 79-93.

ABOUT THE AUTHOR (S)

Dr. Yuvraj D. Nalwade is an Assistant Professor, Vidya Pratishthan's Institute of Information Technology, Pune, Maharashtra, India

Dr. Mahavir Shetiya is an MBA and NET and currently working as Assistant Professor in S.N.G.Institute of Management and Research, Rajgurunagar, approved by AICTE, New Delhi, Govt. of Maharashtra and affiliated to the Savatribai Phule Pune University, Pune. He has presented and/or published number of Research papers in varied International & National Seminars/Conferences/Journals. He is a corresponding author and can be reached at **mahavirshetiya@gmail.com**.

Dr. Atul Kumar is B.Sc., MBA, M.Phil., PGDIB and Ph.D. He is currently working as an assistant professor in Siddhant College of Engineering, Pune, Maharashtra, which is affiliated to the Savatribai Phule Pune University, Pune.